

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Combining the application of microorganisms with mineral fertilization reduction to improve potato crop quality

The potato (*Solanum tuberosum L.*) is an important crop and one of the world's most popular foods. Current, potato-growing techniques utilize a lot of fertilizers and pesticides, which are costly as well as dangerous for the environment. Co-inoculation of PGPM (Plant Growth-Promoting Microorganisms) or application of commercial formulations with multiple microorganisms can reduce chemical fertilizer use. When combined with mineral fertilizers, PGPM formulations improve crop quality, soil fertility, and the microbial environment. Microorganisms indirectly stimulate plant growth by protecting against phytopathogens, thereby reducing the need for chemical fertilizers and pesticides. The objective of this study was to investigate the potential of microorganisms (which in our case

were commercial products of N-fixing and nutrient-solubilizing bacteria and fungi) as a partial replacement for mineral fertilizer, to improve soil health and potato crop performance. Four treatments were applied: a) F100 (conventional fertilization); b) BA+FU (nutrient solubilizing bacteria and fungi + 50% of fertilization reduction); c) BA (nutrient solubilizing bacteria + 50% of fertilization reduction); d) F50 (only 50% of fertilization reduction). We observed a tendency to improve potato mean weight (g), size distribution ($V\text{ cm}^{-3}$), flesh firmness (Kg cm^{-2}), and starch content (%) in the plots treated with biofertilizers. Thus, combining the use of biofertilizers with a reduction in chemical fertilizer input could be a long-term strategy for increasing crop yield and profitability.

1. Potato plantation and harvest in Mediterranean South region (Spain).

KEYWORDS

Biofertilizers, conventional fertilization, *Solanum tuberosum L.*, crop quality, crop yield, *Rhizoctonia sp.*

AUTHORSHIP

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